

A GENERAL CONSISTENT APPROACH TO OPTIMIZATION PROBLEMS FOR COMPOSITE LAMINATED STRUCTURES

Aleksander. Muc

Cracow University of Technology, Kraków, Poland

KEYWORDS: Optimisation, Probabilistic Algorithms, Plates, Shells, Numerical Modeling, Fuzzy Environment

INTRODUCTION

Now, composite materials are typically used in various branches of modern industry and it is observed that in many engineering fields there are attempts to replace components with classical, isotropic materials (steel, concrete) by fiber reinforced plastics. However, in order to use their anisotropic properties in an appropriate manner it is always necessary to apply optimisation techniques since the difference between the worst and the best (optimal) solutions may reach even 100% or more. The second still open problem lies in the range of uncertainty of mechanical properties of constructions made of FRP. It is obvious that the optimisation techniques should take into account the possible variability in mechanical properties and in this way it is necessary to predict possible variations of optimal solutions with a change of mechanical properties.

A lot of efforts have been put into introduction and application of effective optimization algorithms in the design of 2-D or 3-D laminated plated and shell structures. On the other hand, due to anisotropy and inhomogeneity these structures shows rather complicated states of stresses and strains such that several adequate mechanical models for composites structures have been developed in recent years - see e.g. [1,2]. However, those models may be successfully implemented into optimisation problems using FE models and procedures only since analytical approach is impossible (e.g. for complicated loading and boundary conditions) or may lead to very complicated formula. Such an analysis have been conducted by the author and presented in Refs [3,4]. In the present paper we intend to focus our attention on the extension of the optimisation analysis into the field of the uncertainty of mechanical properties of composite materials. It will be done with the use of the fuzzy set – the details of the formulation of various mechanical problems for composites in a fuzzy set environment are presented in Ref [5].

A unified, consistent approach to various optimisation problems in a fuzzy environment is based on an appropriate conjunction of four elements: (1) definition and coding of design variables describing the analysed structures, (2) optimisation algorithms, (3) a FE code and (4) a fuzzy set formulation of variability (uncertainty) of mechanical properties. The latter problem is formulated with the use of appropriate membership functions. All mentioned above elements are or may be formulated independently and this is the significant advantage of the proposed approach since using the proposed methodology it is possible to formulate and solve completely different optimisation problems. The flowchart of the general optimisation method with the use of the numerical FE approach is demonstrated in Fig. 1.

In the present paper various numerical optimisation problems have been solved to illustrate the effectiveness and generality of the proposed methods. They deal with stacking sequence optimisation of cylindrical panels and shape optimisation of rectangular plates.

Fig.1 The flowchart of the general, numerical optimisation scheme

DESIGN VARIABLES

Let the the m -component vector of the design variables (s_1, s_2, \dots, s_m) belongs to the m -dimensional set Ω . Dependly on the definition of the domain Ω one can distinguish the following types of design vector (variables): (1) *Discrete variables* – the domain Ω is a set of discrete variables, e.g. a set of natural numbers $\{1, 2, 3\}$ and (2) *Continuous variables* – the domain Ω is a set (or a subset) of real (complex) numbers, e.g. we are looking for the optimal fibre orientations θ_i belonging to the interval of real numbers $[0^\circ, 90^\circ]$. All types of design variables (continuous and discrete) discussed in the paper are treated as discrete variables since they are represented (coded) as discrete numbers. It is directly connected with the use of the probabilistic nature of optimisation algorithms. On the other hand, it should be mentioned also that for composites the discrete representations of fibre orientations is required due to possible simplifications of technological processes.

Different types of the design variables exists dependly on the formulation of the functional objectives. In order to clarify various approaches the present introduced herein classification is directly connected with the FE coding of individual elements in the mesh. Thus, the type of discrete variables is directly determined by the introduced method of numerical discretization for analysed structures. One can distinguish the following variables:

1. *Topological variables* defining the connectivity of particular structural elements in the structure; in the paper it denotes the stacking sequence of the individual layers in the laminate understood in the sense of the sequence of layers having prescribed discrete fibre orientations θ_i in each individual ply in the laminate; commonly, it is assumed that the thicknesses of individual plies are identical, i.e. $t_i = t/N$, where t denotes the total thickness of the laminate, whereas N means the total number of plies, and $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$ - see Fig.2.

Fig. 2 Topological variables for laminated multilayered cylindrical panels

2. *Geometrical variables* characterizing the geometry of structures in the sense of the nodal points coordinates (positions) in the FE mesh; they are associated with the structural shape optimisation problems understood herein in the broader sense, i.e. as: a) shape optimisation of the external boundaries of structures, b) shape optimisation of the whole structures, particularly in the case of axisymmetric structures where their shapes is defined similarly as previously by the curve .In both cases the shape can be uniquely determined by one or more curves – see Fig.3. The curve C is defined by a finite number of so-called key-points joined with the use of the Bezier spline function – see Fig.4.

Fig. 3 Geometrical variables: a) shape optimisation of external boundaries, b) shape optimisation of axisymmetric structures

3. *Material variables* describing both thicknesses of finite elements and their mechanical properties (in the sense of material constants); in the limit case it may lead to the elimination of the individual FE from the initial mesh as its Young's modulus is equal to zero; as it will be demonstrated later thicknesses and mechanical properties can be smeared out over the whole structure using the finite number of key-points and the Bezier spline functions.

Fig. 4 The curve C representing distributions of geometrical or material design variables(6 key-points)

In order to assure a great flexibility and generality in formulation of various optimisation problems different types of discrete design variables must be represented in a similar unified manner, i.e. each design variable must be coded as a finite string of digits. For topological variables it may be done easily using the method presented in Fig. 2. Let us note that the angle-ply antymmetric laminates are considered only, however, it can be easily extended for arbitrary laminate configuration. Using that method of coding one can introduce more allowable fibre orientations – see Fig.2 where: 1 represents 0°_2 , 2 – $\pm 22.5^\circ_2$, 3 – $\pm 45^\circ_2$, 4 – $\pm 67.5^\circ_2$, 5 – 90°_2 . Each design variable s representing fibre orientation (i.e. 1, 2 or 3 in Fig.4) is coded as binary number and called as a gen. The sequence {1,2,1,3} in Fig.2 is called as a chromosome.

For shape and material variables the distributions of searched design variables are controlled by the positions of a very limited number of vertices (key points P_1, P_2, P_3, \dots etc.) – see Fig.4. The position of each key points is characterized by one real variable. The location of each key point (called as a

gen) is expressed by a chain of 0 and 1 numbers. For instance if the radius r is represented by seven digits that the string (0,0,0,0,0,0,0) is equivalent to the real number s_{min} , whereas the string (1,1,1,1,1,1,1) to the number s_{max} . In this way the interval $[s_{min}, s_{max}]$ is divided into 2^7 subintervals where the end of each subinterval is coded by a seven digit string being a combination of 0 and 1. Increasing the number of digits in the string one can obtain more dense division of the initial interval $[s_{min}, s_{max}]$. Thus, the so-called chromosome contains information about the location of key points (i.e. design variables s_i) in ordered form, starting from the first one and can be written in the following form:

$$chromosome = \left\langle \underbrace{00110110110110011001110110011011001101100110110011011001}_{s_1} \underbrace{10110110110110011001110110011011001101100110110011011001}_{s_2} \underbrace{10110110110110011001110110011011001101100110110011011001}_{s_3} \underbrace{10110110110110011001110110011011001101100110110011011001}_{s_4} \underbrace{10110110110110011001110110011011001101100110110011011001}_{s_5} \underbrace{10110110110110011001110110011011001101100110110011011001}_{s_6} \right\rangle \quad (1)$$

Then, using the Bezier spline approximation technique the distributions of design variables is represented in a functional continuous form. Such an approximation technique may be used not only for the evaluation of 1-D curves (boundaries of 2-D structures) but also for 2-D curves being boundaries of 3-D bodies. Dependly on the further assumption and construction of the curve C the curve lies in a convex hull of the vertices or not.

Dependly on the analysed optimisation problem (Table 2) the binary coding of design variables is used with the aid of the incidence matrix introduced in the form given in Table 1. The total number of columns represents the length of the chromosome. Each gen in the chromosome describes the coded information in rows, i.e. if $a(1,1)=1$ then the ply orientation is equal to 0^0 , and if $a(2,1)=a(3,1)=0$ then the ply orientation is not equal to 45^0 (or 90^0 , rsp.) etc. Shape optimisation is connected with searching for optimal structural boundaries, whereas topology optimisation is mainly associated with the minimum mass (volume) problems taking into account the area occupied by a structure, its thickness and/or density of fibres in the construction.

1	0	0	0	0
0	0	1	1	0
0	1	0	0	0

Table 1. The form of the incidence matrix $a(i,j)$

Optimisation Problem	Row	Column
Stacking sequence	Orientation	Ply Number
Shape	Position	Number of Key Point
Topology	Existence of FE	Number of FE

Table 2. The physical sense of the terms in the incidence matrix

OPTIMISATION IN A FUZZY SET ENVIROMENT

The optimum design in a fuzzy environment is a new approach although some attempts have been made in this area starting from the pioneering works of Zimmermann [6], Rao [7,8], Verdegay [9], Yazenin [10], Yeh & Hsu [11]. An application of fuzzy sets to optimization problems of structures made of composite materials have been given by Morton & Weber [12], Adali [13]. For a fuzzy optimization problem the fuzzy objective function and constraints are characterized by their membership functions.

In the Table 3 there are compared two optimization problems deterministic and fuzzy. Of course, the minimum design problem may be simply reformulated to the maximum problem. As it may be noticed the definition of the constraints seems to be the difference in both formulations. However, as it will be

demonstrated below the significant difference lies in the optimization algorithms and the reformulation of the fuzzy optimum design problems, since in a fuzzy environment searching for the optimum solutions is carried out not for the values of design variables s (a crisp problem) but for the membership functions.

	Deterministic (crisp) formulation	Fuzzy formulation
Objective	Find: Min $f(s)$	Find: Min $f(s)$
Constraints	$g_j(s) \leq b_j, j = 1, 2, \dots, m$	$g_j(s) \in G_j$ (fuzzy sets), $j=1, 2, \dots, m$

s – design variables (a vector)

Table 3 Comparison of the deterministic and fuzzy optimization problems

The fuzzy feasible region A is defined by considering all the constraints, i.e.:

$$A = \bigcap_{j=1}^m G_j \quad (2)$$

and the membership degree of any design variables s to a fuzzy feasible region A is given by the following condition :

$$\mu_A(s) = \text{Min}_j \{ \mu_{g_j}(s) \} \quad (3)$$

that means the minimum degree of satisfaction of the design variables s to all the constraints. A design variables can be considered as feasible if the objective function defines a non-empty fuzzy set $D \subset A$ being the intersection of the membership functions of the objective and the constraints, such that:

$$D = \{ \mu_f(s) \} \cap \left\{ \bigcap_{j=1}^m \mu_{g_j}(s) \right\} \quad (4)$$

From the fuzzy set the optimum solution \bar{s} is selected as the design for which the membership is a maximum (see Fig.5), i.e.:

$$\mu_D(\bar{s}) = \text{Max} \mu_D(s) = \text{Max} [\text{Min} (\mu_f(s), \mu_{g_1}(s), \dots, \mu_{g_m}(s))] \quad (5)$$

Fig. 5 Optimal fuzzy decision-making

Fig. 6 Form of the membership function $\mu(x)$ (the Gaussian curve)

Thus, using the fuzzy formulation the initial minimum problem (see Table 2) is formulated as a MinMax problem. The latter problem is reformulated to the following maximum problem introducing an additional objective λ :

$$\text{Find Max } \lambda \quad (6)$$

subject to the constraints:

$$\lambda \leq \mu_f(s), \quad \lambda \leq \mu_{g_j}, j=1,2,\dots,m \quad (7)$$

The analysis conducted in a fuzzy set environment is strongly dependant on the assumed form of the membership function $\mu(x)$. For our purposes that function is prescribed in the form of the Gaussian curve (Fig.6) where the mean value corresponds to the value of the parameter assumed in the traditional optimisation (called as the deterministic (crisp) optimisation in Table 3), whereas the standard deviation, characterizing the uncertainty in the description of parameters is equal to 10%. In numerical examples the mechanical properties of composite materials will be treated as fuzzy numbers so that the description of their membership functions via Gaussian curves is in a very good agreement with the variation of experimental data.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

Stacking Sequence Optimisation of Cylindrical Laminated Panels

Let us consider a multilayered laminated shallow cylindrical panel clamped along its edges in the longitudinal direction. Geometrical parameters defining the structure are demonstrated in Fig. 7.

Fig.7. Geometry of a cylindrical panel.

The numerical analysis have been conducted for the panels having the following geometrical: $L=150$, $R=100$, $f=6.03$, $\varphi=20^\circ$ and material: $E_1 = 84$ GPa, $E_2 = E_3 = 12$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = 0.25$,

$G_{12} = G_{23} = G_{13} = 7.8$ GPa properties. The shell have been modeled with the use of 420 quadrilateral four noded elements including transverse shear effects. The laminate wall have been made of 16 layers so that each chromosome consists of four different gens according to the laminate representation discussed in the section 2. Three possible fibre orientations are analysed herein, i.e. 0° , 45° and 90° .

Figure 8 shows the variations of natural frequencies with the wavenumbers m, n , and Figure 9 represents the variations of the lowest natural frequency with the fiber orientations for angle ply panel. In the optimisation problem we are looking for the minimal natural frequency with respect to fibre orientations, :

$$\text{Min } \omega(s) \tag{8}$$

where s denotes the discretised set of fibre orientations.

For angle-ply cylindrical panels the minimum corresponds to fibers oriented at 0° (see Fig. 9). Increasing number of design variables and applying the probabilistic algorithms it was found that the lowest value of natural frequency for free vibration problem corresponds to the laminate configuration $[1,1,1,1]$ – the crisp deterministic formulation, i.e. the same as for the angle-ply laminates and it is associated with the first mode of vibrations. However, the next modes lies very close to the first one since: 2 – 6.79 KHz, 3 – 8.29 kHz, 4 – 10.62 kHz, 5 – 13.67 kHz. Therefore, it is interesting and important from the engineering point of view to consider how to formulate the optimisation problem: searching for the minimal value of natural frequency or for the maximal one.

Fig. 8. Values of optimal free vibrations for cylindrical shells

Fig.9. Free vibrations vs. fibre orientations

Taking into account the fuzzy set formulation of the optimisation problem where three material properties Young's and Kirchoff's moduli are expressed in the form of the membership functions (Fig.6) the optimal stacking sequence [1,1,1,1] has not been changed but the increase of the optimal free vibrations satisfying the relation (7) has been observed. It should be emphasized that the results are valid for the assumed shell geometry. Further analysis is needed to consider the influences of geometry which may be significant for some optimisation problems given by eqn (8). It should be mentioned also that in our optimisation problem there is no constraints as in the general formulation given by eqn (7).

Shape optimisation of holes in rectangular plates

In mathematical terms the objective of optimisation problem is following:

To find:

$$\text{Min}(\text{Max}U) \text{ over feasible shapes } C, \quad (9)$$

subjected to the constraints:

- the total area enclosed by the curve C is constant,
- the curve C is a convex.

The functional U may be defined in different ways, however for our purposes it will be taken in the form of the strain energy density. The curve C is defined by the positions of the key points - being design variables of our optimisation problem.

To demonstrate the effectiveness of our optimization methodology let us consider the plate with a hole subjected to an uniform tension along its edges – see Fig. 10. The plate is made of orthotropic material having the following material properties: $E_x = 345$ [GPa], $E_y = 105.2$ [GPa], $G_{xy} = 40$ [GPa], $\nu_{xy}=0.3$. The identical example have been solved by Muc [14] using linear programming optimization methods.

Fig. 8 Definition of geometrical parameters for the design problem

Fig. 9 Optimal shapes for the crisp and fuzzy solutions

In our fuzzy optimization problem let us assume the possible variability of the plate mechanical properties leading to the variations of the moduli E_x , E_y , G_{xy} in the form given by the Gaussian curve

– Fig.6. The constraints are assumed to be in the deterministic (not fuzzy) form. The results are plotted in Fig. 11. The crisp results is compared with two cases of the left-most and of the right-most variations of the mechanical properties. As it may be observed there is no symmetry with the respect to the $\alpha=1$ solution (the optimal deterministic crisp solution).

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The possibility of unified general approach to various types of discrete optimisation problems and variables have been formulated and studied. The proposed method is based on the concept of the incidence matrix representation of design variables joined with the probabilistic optimisation algorithms and finite element packages. For shape and material optimisation problems the Bezier spline approximation technique seems to be a powerful tool in the design variables representation. Such an approach allows us to include automatically different constraint conditions dealing with the convexity of approximated curves not only in the deterministic (crisp) optimisation approach but also in a fuzzy set environment.

Various numerical examples demonstrate the effectiveness of the introduced formulation. They concern stacking sequence and shape optimisation problems. The possibility of evaluation of any required objectives with the prescribed correctness of theoretical modeling and numerical accuracy is the most important and promising effect of the approach. However, the latter is strongly dependant on the availability of the appropriate finite element packages.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is funded by the State Committee for Scientific Research (KBN) under Grant No. PB-0829/T07/2002/23

REFERENCES

- [1] Bendsoe, M., P., (1995), *Optimization of Structural Topology, Shape and Material*, Springer-Verlag, Heidelberg.
- [2] Christiansen, R. M. (1979) *Mechanics of Composite Materials*, Wiley, New York.
- [3] Muc, A., Gurba, W. (2001) Genetic algorithms and finite element analysis in optimization of composite structures, *Composite Structures*, 54, pp. 275-281.
- [4] Muc, A., Gurba, W.; Fugiel T., Kędziora P. (2002), Discrete Optimisation of 2-D Laminated Composite Plate and Shell Structures, *Proc. 6th Int. Conf. Computational Str. Technology*, Prague
- [5] Muc A., Kędziora P.,(2003) Application of Fuzzy Set Theory in Mechanics of Composite Materials, in *Soft Computing in Textile Sciences* (L.M.Sztandera, Ch.Pastore eds), Physica-Verlag, Heidelberg, New York, pp.16-50.
- [6] Zimmermann H.J. (1976), Description and optimization of fuzzy systems, *International Journal of General Systems*, 2, no. 4, pp. 209-215.
- [7] Rao S.S. (1987), Multi-objective optimization of fuzzy structural systems, *International Journal for numerical Methods in Engineering*, 24, pp. 1157-1171.

- [8] Rao S.S. (1992), Fuzzy goal programming approach for structural optimization, *AIAA Journal*, 30, no. 5, pp. 1425-1432.
- [9] Verdegay J.L. (1982), Fuzzy mathematical programming, *Fuzzy Information and Design Process* (Edited by M. M. Gupta and E. Sanchez), North-Holland, Amsterdam.
- [10] Yazenin A.V. (1987), Fuzzy and stochastic programming, *Fuzzy Sets Syst.*, 22, pp. 171-180.
- [11] Yeh Y.C. and Hsu D.S. (1988), *Structural optimization with uncertainty factors*, Twelfth National Conference on Theoretical and Applied Mechanics, Taipei, Taiwan, R.O.C., pp. 565-571.
- [12] Morton S.K. and Webber J.P.H. (1990), Uncertainty reasoning applied to the assessment of composite materials for structural design, *Engineering Optimization*, 16, pp. 43-77.
- [13] Adali S. (1991), Fuzzy optimization of laminated cylindrical pressure vessels, *Composite Structures*, Elsevier Applied Science, Londyn, pp. 249-260.
- [14] Muc, A. (1998) Effectiveness of Optimal Design with respect to Computational Models for Laminated Composite Structures Weakened by Holes, *Structural Optimization*, 16, pp.58-67.